

DOJEMANJE TAJVANSKIH ŠTUDENTOV O MEDKULTURNIH INTERAKCIJAH V KONTEKSTU AKADEMSKE DIPLOMACIJE

Razširjen povzetek

Namen: Konferenčni članek raziskuje dojemanje tajvanskih študentov o medkulturnih interakcijah z mednarodnimi študenti v akademskem okolju.

Cilj: Cilj te študije je analizirati, kako študentje na Tajvanu doživljajo medkulturno interakcijo v kontekstu izobraževanja kot mehke moči.

Metodologija: To je kvalitativna raziskovalna študija, osredotočena na zbiranje in analizo podatkov iz polstrukturiranih intervjujev za preučevanje elementov mehke moči v mednarodnih učilnicah na Tajvanu.

Ugotovitve raziskave: Ugotovitve raziskave kažejo na pogled tajvanskih študentov na medkulturne interakcije v mednarodnih in visokošolskih učilnicah na Nacionalni univerzi v Tajpeju.

Znanstvena vrednost: Prispevek k razumevanju medkulturne interakcije v kontekstu akademske diplomacije je pomemben. S preučevanjem dojemanja tajvanske študentske populacije gostiteljev o mednarodnih izmenjavah nudimo dokaze, kako lahko takšna interakcija oblikuje trende mehke moči v visokem šolstvu.

Praktična vrednost: Prispevek daje oblikovalcem izobraževalne politike in upravi razumevanje prednosti in izzivov učinkovitih mednarodnih programov, ki so del strategije ministrstva za izobraževanje Tajvana.

Omejitve raziskave: vzorec in zbrani podatki morda ne predstavljajo v celoti raznolikosti dojemanja in izkušenj tajvanskih študentov z mednarodnimi vrstniki. Tudi za to konferenco študija nima dovolj prostora, da bi zajela vse elemente teorije mehke moči.

Ključne besede: akademska diplomacija, mehka moč, medkulturna interakcija.

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PERCEPTION OF TAIWANESE STUDENTS ON CROSS-CULTURAL INTERACTION IN THE CONTEXT OF ACADEMIC DIPLOMACY

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Extended summary

Purpose: The conference article explores Taiwanese students' perceptions of cross-cultural interactions with international students in academic settings.

Objective: This study's objective is to analyze how students in Taiwan experience cross-cultural interaction within the context of education as a soft power.

Methodology: This is a qualitative research study focused on gathering and analyzing data from semi-structured interviews to examine soft power elements in international classrooms in Taiwan.

Research findings: The research findings indicate Taiwan students' view on cross-cultural interactions in international and higher education classrooms at the National Taipei University.

Scientific value: There is value in contribution to the understanding of cross-cultural interaction within the context of academic diplomacy. Examining Taiwan's host student population's perceptions of international exchanges, we provide evidence of how such interaction can shape soft power trends in higher education.

Practical value: The contribution provides education policymakers and administration with an understanding of the benefits and challenges of effective international programs that are part of the Ministry of Education of Taiwan's strategy.

Research limitations: The sample and collected data may not fully represent the diversity of Taiwanese students' perceptions and experiences with international peers. Also, for this conference, the study does not have enough space to cover all elements of Soft Power theory.

Keywords: academic diplomacy, soft power, cross-cultural interaction.

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Introduction

International education offers a wide range of benefits, including knowledge acquisition, students' cosmopolitan competencies, and cultural knowledge. It also develops students' global citizenship by broadening their horizons and enriches course curriculums and research activities. The internationalization of higher education leads to skill development and contributes to home countries by bringing students and academics from other countries by making international settings right at 'home' (Seebar et al., 2016; Singh, 2018; Ahwireng, 2022).

The internationalization of higher education (HE) has taken a business dimension, with academic institutions embracing commercial practices to stay competitive on the global stage and gain a higher rank in the overall international system (Kabeera, 2019). In some countries, higher education has become a profitable business.

For Asian economies, an influx of international students ensures high quality to keep up with competition from countries such as the United States (Levent, 2016). One of the leading countries in this trend is Taiwan.

Among students from all over the world who are coming to study the Chinese language for shorter periods. There are more and more international colleges that offer international programs and English-taught courses across different academic disciplines.

The study here analyzes how host Taiwanese students perceive and experience cross-cultural interaction in the context of academic diplomacy in higher education in their courses in classrooms. The research aims to understand how these changes contribute to the soft power of educational institutions in Taiwan.

Academic diplomacy is a significant factor that enhances international education collaborations, promotes cultural understanding, cultivates positive relations between countries, establishes trust, and advances mutual understanding among current and future generations (Mencia-Ripley, 2021).

The research question of this study is - How do Taiwanese students perceive cross-cultural interaction with international students concerning soft power factors – social interaction and integration and academic diplomacy?

Literature review

Internationalization of Taiwan Higher Education

Official statistics from the Ministry of Education in Taiwan have indicated Taiwanese students' unstoppable trend to study abroad. The number of students studying overseas during 2022 was 53,510. Taiwanese students have been recorded as being in the pursuit of a degree or a non-degree program at overseas universities. Among the students, the top three destinations with the most Taiwanese registered students have consistently been the United States, followed by Australia and Japan (Ministry of Education, 2023a).

On another note, Taiwan has been welcoming a large number of international students. Over the years, the Ministry of Education has endeavored to gain a competitive edge in attracting global talents, fostering research capacities, and creating a sound investment environment for domestic and multinational corporations (Ministry of Education, 2023b). In particular, between the years 2014 and 2023, approximately between 91,000 and 130,000 students have been registered in universities in Taiwan. The number has constantly stayed above 100,000 except for the academic year 2021 and 2022 as a result of rigorous pandemic restrictions in Taiwan. In terms of inbound students, ASEAN [Association of Southeast Asian Nations] countries, Hong Kong, and Japan have emerged as the primary contributors to the student population since 2020. Another trend highlight is the steady increase of international students for a degree program, leaping from 14,063 in 2014 to 37,061 in 2023 (Ministry of Education, 2023c, 2023d).

The Association of International Cultural and Educational Exchange Taiwan (AICEE Taiwan) reported a survey of 2,000 students from 60 countries who intend to study abroad to study. The top three advantages of Taiwan include high-quality education, a safe environment, and the opportunity to learn the Mandarin language. For students to study abroad in Taiwan, the most critical factors are scholarships in the first place, then entirely English-thought programs and teaching quality. Mr. Allen Hung, The Chief Executive Officer of AICEE Taiwan, advised Taiwan Universities to provide essential enrollment information and reinforce information about internships and job opportunities during studies and after graduation (AICEE Taiwan, 2024).

Academic Diplomacy

Academic diplomacy is a quite new term, and it can be easily confused with science diplomacy, knowledge diplomacy, and education diplomacy. While academic diplomacy has an overall role and reaching out to the community with its activities, other mentioned forms of diplomacy are more focused on how to address common problems between countries in a scientific way, or knowledge sharing, and establishing long-term student relations through educational diplomacy (Gliboa 20028: Hill et al 2016; Jooste, Hangenmeier, 2022). Today we speak about all these phenomena since they became important instruments in international relations, particularly for small states looking to compensate for limited military and economic capabilities. The biggest power of small states is diplomacy in any sense.

Academic diplomacy, also known as diplomacy of academia, refers to the use of educational tools and collaborations by nations to cultivate positive relationships, establish trust, and enhance mutual understanding. It involves engaging in knowledge exchange, student programs, joint research projects, and the establishment of educational institutions abroad to promote cultural engagement and soft power strategies (Lubina, 2021). It means that academic diplomacy uses a soft power approach to academia to promote 'prevention-driven' and action-based activities that can bring academic and non-academic collaboration to generate basic social changes, social innovation, and cross-cultural understanding which leads to wider economic and even diplomatic changes.

Soft Power in Higher Education

One of the primary reasons academic diplomacy is essential in a higher education setting is its role in promoting soft power.

Soft Power Theory by Josephs S Nye (2004. 2021) is the ability to influence others to achieve desired outcomes through attraction and persuasion rather than in a 'hard' way by force or payment. It is based on intangible factors such as culture, political values, and foreign policies that make a country appealing to others. All that should contribute to the attractiveness of the country and influence on the global stage. Soft power is a complex and multifaced concept that combines various elements working together to enhance country, or today's city influences in the global international sphere.

As Gauttam et al (2021) state higher institutions act as instruments of soft power, creating national goodwill, appeal, and attraction among individuals from different countries. By promoting their education systems and facilitating student exchanges, countries can enhance their reputation and influence globally, and in that way strengthen their soft power capabilities (Zielinska, 2016, 2021; Antonova et al 2020).

Cross-cultural interactions as a tool for academic diplomacy

Cross-cultural interaction and academic diplomacy are essential in international relations, facilitating mutual understanding, trust-building, and cooperation between nations. Academic exchanges, like scientific, educational, and cultural collaborations are considered vital components of international relations that can contribute to conflict resolutions and international harmony (Alzugaray, 20026; Saaida, 2023).

Cross-cultural interactions play a crucial role in enhancing a country's soft power. They stimulate cultural exchange through dialog and mutual activities which help bridge and understand different political systems, social values, nations, institutions, and ideas and foster understanding and empathy (Saaida, 2023).

Hence, the cross-cultural interactions facilitated by academic diplomacy can enhance a country's soft power. Students with positive experiences may return to their homes with positive experiences, views, and possible long-lasting friendships of the country, society, and nation they were hosted by. In that way, cross-cultural interactions contribute to soft power.

Research Plan

This research is qualitative exploratory kind, and it is based on semi-structured interviews collected from Taiwanese students who share their classroom in fully English thought courses at National Taipei University (NTPU). The interviewees were 13 students from undergraduate studies. They are all 18 to 23 years of age and from different majors (Law, Real Estate, Social science, Humanities, Engineering, Foreign languages Applied Linguistics, etc.). Interviewees were selected from the current courses of Dr. Klicek, and through an open call on the inner university NTPU network. Each interview lasted approximately 40 minutes to 1 hour.

Thirteen students attended the interviews in April 2024. Interview questions were based on elements of the Soft Power Theory by Joseph S. Nye (Nye, 2004, 2019). Categories of questions aligned with Soft Power Theory elements included questions about differences in culture, political values, and foreign policies. Questions related to academic diplomacy were included to delve into the subject further. Additionally, social interactions were incorporated into the discussion, even though they are not explicitly identified as a tool of soft power in the Soft Power theory. However, social interactions are vital for expressing and expanding soft power in any context.

After the interviews, verbatim transcripts in Mandarin Chinese were created. A subsequent thematic analysis was performed on MAXQDA based on the transcripts from 13 interviews. Table 1. Show reflections of Taiwanese students' perceptions of international intercultural encounters in the classrooms. Due to the extensive nature of the topic, only 2 elements are presented.

Table 1. Interview Coding Scheme – two elements of Soft power social interaction and integration and academic diplomacy

Theme	Codes	Frequency
Social Interaction and Integration	Taiwanese People's Misunderstandings on International Students' Behavior	8*
	Different Values (Taiwan vs. Other Countries)	6
Academic Diplomacy	Reasons for International Students to Taiwan	25
	Measures to Improve Inclusion in Taiwan	23

*Frequency means that during 13 interviews the codes were repeated 8 times by students

Results

Below are the results and some interesting findings on how Taiwanese students perceive their cross-cultural interaction with international students in terms of two factors of soft power – social interaction and integration and academic diplomacy. Table 2 displays selected quotes regarding social interaction and integration in cross-cultural settings. It highlights how international students may be deemed to enjoy greater freedom and autonomy without thinking about how to behave like the rest of the group.

Table 2: Students' Perceptions of Social Interaction and Integration in Cross-Cultural Settings

Codes	Answers	Comments
Different Values (Taiwan vs. Other Countries)	I think the values of the culture may still be different from ours; that is, Americans may attach more importance to individual freedom and less importance to the interests of the organization.	Both excerpts present how Taiwanese students perceive freedom. In most of the interviews, the US is mentioned as the beacon of freedom.
	Taiwan's freedom is still a bit different from the American freedom. Perhaps Freedom in the US equates to violence? There may be guns or bullying, and their freedom of speech is a little bit too radical sometimes. I can't say that this won't happen in Taiwan, but in Taiwan, our freedom is based on respect. Perhaps it is because Confucianism has a vast influence on us. We tend not to overdo things, so our freedom is a great advantage.	
Taiwanese People's Misunderstandings on International Students' Behavior	I was a student buddy for a smoker, and he wondered why he couldn't smoke on campus. He told me that in his country, they used to smoke in the classroom, and everyone smelled it together. He probably thought that some rules in Taiwan made her feel confused about why everyone was so disciplined.	This excerpt that the Taiwanese people are obliged to consider others and avoid being different to achieve interpersonal harmony.
	I'm a little confused because my friend skipped her midterm and went to Bali. I will not do that. Although he is an exchange student, I can't understand the behavior of skipping midterms and going to Bali to have fun.	

Table 3 shows answers to students' perceptions of academic diplomacy.

Table 3: Students' Perceptions on Academic Diplomacy

Codes	Answers	Comments
Reasons for International Students to Taiwan	I know a Somalilander and a Liswati (a person from Eswatini). They came to Taiwan because of a scholarship. They wanted to go to the US, but the US is very expensive, so they came to Taiwan. Many students are like that. I've known people who cheated their way here by telling them the amount of scholarship sounded big, but then once they were here it was not high enough for good student life in Taiwan.	Financial affordability is the primary concern for international students. The French student was also no exception.
	The tuition fees in Hong Kong are too expensive for me to pay. I couldn't afford the (NT)\$200,000 a year in Hong Kong, so I came here.	
	China is more autocratic; I think that Taiwan is more democratic and freer, so foreign students are more daring to come to Taiwan. The reason foreign students may want to come here may be ... a Chinese-speaking country that is considered to be free because China is a bit more autocratic.	Several Taiwanese students mentioned this issue because of their assumptions about what international students think and what might be one of the reasons they chose Taiwan.
Measures to Improve Inclusion in Taiwan	Language creates quite a significant barrier. If people know that I communicate in English, ok, but if they don't speak Chinese, they may feel a little bit like, "You don't speak our language, so that's more of an obstacle, and then we live you to live aside of us."	Students believe that language hinders international students who want to acclimate to life in Taiwan.
	When I read Chinese websites, I get a lot of information, but much information is missing from English websites. Foreign students do not know it, but then they don't get the complete picture of how it is here.	
	I know I shouldn't change my attitude because of someone's nationality. Also, respecting their culture is important. There are more international migrant workers from Southeast Asia in Taiwan, but there has been a stereotypical image of Southeast Asian students. I think we can work on that a bit.	For Taiwanese students, a step to inclusion for students from different backgrounds lies in non-verbal acts, and not only in languages.

Discussion

The study presents Taiwanese students' perceptions of cross-cultural interaction. In this study we focused on social interaction and integration and academic diplomacy was presented.

Taiwanese students may consider international students overly free without considering others. While freedom is valued in Taiwan, only when respect exists can it qualify the enjoyment of it. Additionally, Taiwanese students believe that liberty is not a license to be irresponsible. Nevertheless, the context differs when it comes to the difference between exchange students and international

students, as stated in the following interview excerpt, “Are exchange students more free-spirited? For example, you can go to Taitung this weekend if you want to do something. But if you’re an international student for a degree, you don’t seem different from us.”.

Academic diplomacy in the opinion of Taiwanese students means scholarship tuitions have seemed to attract students from worldwide. Comparisons suggest that the cost of attending a university is US\$99,417 for four years, with tuition and living costs considered monumental in the US (Bridgestock, 2023). In contrast, Taiwan costs students US\$32,160 for a four-year degree (Billman, 2023). Additionally, while the tuition for Hong Kongers to attend a government-sponsored university is HK\$42,100 (US\$1,300) per academic year (JUPAS, n.d.), yearly living cost in Hong Kong is approximately HK\$ 138,500 (US\$17,730) (Hong Kong Baptist University, n.d.). Therefore, Taiwan students think that Taiwan is quite an affordable place to live in study.

On the other hand, with the exchange of people, an open and diverse environment can necessitate academic diplomacy. Students are aware of the need to build an inclusive environment. Language can be a decisive factor. Relevant to previous discussions on languages (Chu et al., 2017), the use of English must be prevalent, and exposure to Mandarin Chinese should be granted to international students. Beyond languages, efforts to minimize stereotypes and discrimination are in progress, yet implicit acts (e.g., a peculiar gaze on international students and few meal options) suggest international students’ discomfort. Moreover, initiatives to extend friendliness and being friendly need to be done.

Note, however, that this research poses some caveats as only undergraduate students from National Taipei University were interviewed. And only those who take some English language courses at this university. It would be great to see what students who stick only to Chinese courses think about intercultural communication and foreign students whom they see a lot in campus..

Conclusion

This study’s findings provide insights into Taiwanese students’ perceptions and experiences as hosts regarding cross-cultural interactions with international students in academic settings. Taiwanese students value their freedom but also believe in the importance of respect. They acknowledge the differences between exchange students and those seeking a degree abroad. Unlike the United States and Hong Kong, Taiwan offers lower tuition fees and scholarships, which is why it attracts many international students.

It is crucial to create an inclusive environment that promotes both English and Mandarin usage while also working towards reducing stereotypes and discrimination.

The contribution to educational institutions in Taiwan is enhancing their global visibility and reputation through high education as a soft power. By recognizing the importance of academic diplomacy, Taiwan can further build up its soft power even more and strengthen its position in the global education stage.

The findings of the study provide practical information for policymakers and administration, offering them a deeper understanding of the benefits and challenges of additive international programs. The research contributed to the ongoing discussion on soft power and its application in the educational field, where education becomes a part of soft power.

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